

SOLVING A PATH PLANNING PROBLEM USING THE FRONTIER OF VORONOI DIAGRAM WITH TWO SITES AND A CIRCULAR OBSTACLE

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Resumo

O problema de planejamento de caminhos tem sido estudado há muito tempo. Nesta nota, determinamos analiticamente e computacionalmente a estrutura para a fronteira do Diagrama de Voronoi em um determinado caso não linear (formato de obstáculo): um obstáculo circular e dois pontos geradores. Avaliamos e mostramos as equações que determinam a fronteira e o pseudocódigo para a solução computacional. Como solução analítica, encontramos as equações cujo zero é o ponto da fronteira. Como Solução computacional, usamos o método Newton-Raphson. Além disso, traçamos a fronteira em alguns casos diferentes, alterando os seguintes parâmetros: centro do círculo e a localização dos pontos geradores.

Palavras-chaves: Diagrama de Voronoi, Obstáculo Circular, Planejamento de Caminho.

1. Introduction

The Voronoi diagram is widely studied since 1854, [1]. In the two dimensional case it can be intuitively defined as: given a finite set of points in \mathbb{R}^2 , that can be called generating points, the Voronoi diagram of these points is a collection of regions, each one related to a generating point. All points that lie inside one region are closer to its generating point than to any other generating point. Also, the points that belong to the boundaries between two regions have the same distance from their generating points.

Many applications of Voronoi diagram can be found in the literature. In [2] the authors present the allocation problem in a heterogeneous space Voronoi diagram and this work also offers a good survey on allocation problems using Voronoi diagrams. An application in deep learning models in biomedicine can be found at [3]. In [4] Voronoi diagram is used to predict travel time. Another application that appears in [5] uses Voronoi diagram for internet of things. Also an application towards cost-effective 3D printing can be seen in [6].

Another field of application which is very important and actual is related to path planning as can be seen in [7], [8], [9], [10], [11]. In the literature it is not uncommon to find results about Voronoi diagram with polygonal obstacles or without obstacles. All the cited articles deal with the obstacles using approximations, which can be its convex hull, for example. Approximations of the obstacles are commonly used however, according to [12], a good approximation of an obstacle can be computationally expensive.

In this work a motivational example is described in order to show an application for this work. Figure 1 displays the situation with a circular obstacle to which the proposed algorithm of this work has been

constructed. In war times, the mankind develops many tools and solutions for problems that have not yet been produced. Our motivational problem correspond to one application for the Voronoi diagram frontier in a war situation. We can think about one application for our result as been the best choice for a humanitarian corridor, which means to choose a corridor where refugees can go out from a city with the most safe way into a war. Such corridor is represented by the Voronoi diagram frontier. The generating points represent the location of the closest enemies from the humanitarian corridor. In this situation, the goal for the refugees can be considered to take on the minimum possible risk which means to walk over the Voronoi diagram frontier. Such way leaves the refugees over points with the same distance for the generating points. Initially, the refugee must run to the Voronoi diagram frontier. Due to the existence of the obstacle, the Voronoi diagram frontier of this work has nonlinear components (see Section 3.1).

In this note we present the algorithm that builds the frontier of Voronoi diagram with two generating points and a circular obstacle. It is important to explicit the frontier between two generating points with a circular obstacle between them because it gives the benefit to know where to move aiming at staying at the same distance of both, which configures a path planning problem. The definition of a Voronoi diagram edge, can be found in [13]. The set of all edges of Voronoi diagram correspond to the its frontier in this note.

The first contribution presented is making explicit the coordinates of the points of interest, which means having their exact location, avoiding the use of approximations. The second contribution is the algorithm that uses the distances between the points of interest and its derivatives in the Newton-Raphson method in order to generate as many points of the Voronoi diagram frontier adressed in this work as one wants. The third contribution is the frontier itself.

2. Material and Methods

In order to solve the proposed problem, the exact coordinates of the main points $Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4, Q_5, Q_6$ and D were calculated. After that, the distances between these points were computed and also their derivatives.

With all the calculations done, they were put at the proposed algorithm. As the Voronoi diagram frontier of this work is not linear, the algorithm uses the Newton Raphson method in order to compute the frontier points. The algorithm was used to solve an instance of the motivational example of humanitarian corridor. The solution gives the frontier of Voronoi diagram which is also the path that has to be made aiming at staying at the same distance from the two generating points which at the example represent the closest enemies.

3. Theory and Calculations

3.1. Graphical representation and coordinates

The Figure 1 shows the main points that are used to determine the Voronoi diagram frontier.

$A = (0, a)$ and $B = (0, b)$ are the generating points and the point $C = (c, 0)$ is the center of the circular obstacle with the following constraints $a > 0, b < 0, -b > a$ and $0 < c < 1$. The coordinates of Q_2 are such that the line segment CQ_2 is orthogonal to the line segment AQ_2 . In the condition that we do not have obstacle the frontier of the Voronoi diagram is the line $A = (0, a)$ and $B = (0, b)$ are the generating points and the point $C = (c, 0)$ is the center of the circular obstacle with the following constraints $a > 0, b < 0, -b > a$ and $0 < c < 1$. The coordinates of Q_2 are such that the line segment CQ_2 is orthogonal to the line segment AQ_2 . In the condition that we do not have obstacle the frontier of the Voronoi diagram is the line $y = \frac{a+b}{2}$ which is the bisector of points A and B . However, in our case many points of the frontier are out of this line. When an object or a person is making a path over the bisector of points A and B going towards the obstacle, there

is a last point over the bisector that belongs to the Voronoi frontier and in this work this point is named D .

Taking $E = (x,y)$ as a point at the frontier, the coordinates of Q_3 and Q_4 are such that line segments EQ_3 and EQ_4 are orthogonal to line segments CQ_3 and CQ_4 respectively. Finally, the coordinates of Q_5 are such that BQ_5 is orthogonal to Q_5C . The point Q_1 will be used in the future in order to determine the frontier of the right side of the obstacle. Besides, the points Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4 and Q_5 are over the circle. In addition they are important to find the points over the frontier.

Figure 1: Main points – frontier of Voronoi diagram

In the next subsections, some propositions are announced and their demonstrations are at the appendix A.

3.1.1. Coordinates of Q_1 and Q_2

Proposition 1. *The coordinates of Q_1 and Q_2 are:*

$$Q_1 = \left(c + \frac{-c + |a|\sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}}{a^2 + c^2}, \frac{-c^2 + c|a|\sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}}{a(a^2 + c^2)} + \frac{1}{a} \right)$$

$$Q_2 = \left(c + \frac{-c - |a|\sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}}{a^2 + c^2}, \frac{-c^2 - c|a|\sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}}{a(a^2 + c^2)} + \frac{1}{a} \right)$$

where $a(a^2 + c^2) \neq 0$ e $(a^2 + c^2 - 1) \geq 0$.

3.1.2. Coordinates of D

Proposition 2. *The coordinates of D are:*

$$D = \left(\frac{\left(\frac{a-b}{2}\right)x_{Q_2}}{a - y_{Q_2}}, \frac{a+b}{2} \right)$$

In this situation the obstacle is in between the points E and B .

3.1.3. Coordinates of Q_3 and Q_4

Proposition 3. *Take $E = (x,y)$ the coordinates of Q_3 and Q_4 are:*

$$Q_3 = \left(c + \frac{(x-c) - |y|\sqrt{y^2 + (c-x)^2 - 1}}{(c-x)^2 + y^2}, \frac{y^2 + (x-c)|y|\sqrt{y^2 + (c-x)^2 - 1}}{y((c-x)^2 + y^2)} \right)$$

$$Q_4 = \left(c + \frac{(x-c) + |y|\sqrt{y^2 + (c-x)^2 - 1}}{(c-x)^2 + y^2}, \frac{y^2 - (x-c)|y|\sqrt{y^2 + (c-x)^2 - 1}}{y((c-x)^2 + y^2)} \right)$$

for $y((c-x)^2 + y^2) \neq 0$ and $y^2 + (c-x)^2 - 1 \geq 0$.

3.1.4. Coordinates of Q_5 and Q_6

The points Q_5 and Q_6 belong to the circular obstacle and their coordinates are such that BQ_5 is orthogonal to CQ_5 and BQ_6 is orthogonal to CQ_6 .

Proposition 4. *The coordinates of Q_5 and Q_6 are:*

$$Q_5 = \left(c + \frac{-c - |b|\sqrt{b^2 + c^2 - 1}}{b^2 + c^2}, \frac{-c^2 - c|b|\sqrt{b^2 + c^2 - 1}}{b(b^2 + c^2)} + \frac{1}{b} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$Q_6 = \left(c + \frac{-c + |b|\sqrt{b^2 + c^2 - 1}}{b^2 + c^2}, \frac{-c^2 + c|b|\sqrt{b^2 + c^2 - 1}}{b(b^2 + c^2)} + \frac{1}{b} \right) \quad (2)$$

for $b(b^2 + c^2) \neq 0$ and $(b^2 + c^2 - 1) \geq 0$.

3.2. Distances

This Subsection brings the distances between the main points presented in figure 1, which are calculated using the coordinates given in Subsection 3.1. Some functions are used in this Subsection in order to shorten the equations that arise in the distances' calculation.

3.2.1. Functions

As the functions are going to be used from the second distance that appears in this Section onwards, they are all displayed below.

$$\phi = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{-c^2 - c|a|\sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}}{a(a^2 + c^2)} = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{c}{a} \cdot \left(\frac{-c - |a|\sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}}{a^2 + c^2} \right) = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{c}{a} \cdot \lambda. \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{-c - |a|\sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}}{a^2 + c^2} \quad (4)$$

$$M_0 = y \quad (5)$$

$$M_1 = y^2 \quad (6)$$

$$M_2 = x - c \quad (7)$$

$$M_3 = c - x = -(x - c) = -M_2 \quad (8)$$

$$M_4 = |y| \quad (9)$$

$$M_5 = y^2 + (x - c)^2 - 1 = M_1 + M_2^2 - 1 \quad (10)$$

$$M_6 = (x - c) - |y| \cdot \sqrt{y^2 + (x - c)^2 - 1} = M_2 - M_4 \cdot \sqrt{M_5} \quad (11)$$

$$M_7 = (c - x)^2 + y^2 = M_1 + M_2^2 \quad (12)$$

$$M_8 = y \cdot ((c - x)^2 + y^2) = M_0 \cdot (M_1 + M_2^2) = M_0 \cdot M_7 \quad (13)$$

$$M_9 = y^2 + (x - c) \cdot |y| \cdot \sqrt{y^2 + (x - c)^2 - 1} = M_1 + M_2 \cdot M_4 \cdot \sqrt{M_5} \quad (14)$$

$$M_{10} = (x - c) + |y| \cdot \sqrt{y^2 + (x - c)^2 - 1} = M_2 + M_4 \cdot \sqrt{M_5} \quad (15)$$

$$M_{11} = M_1 - M_2 \cdot M_4 \cdot \sqrt{M_5} \quad (16)$$

3.2.2. Computation of the euclidean distance between A and Q_2 .

Proposition 5. The distance between the points A and Q_2 is:

$$d(A, Q_2) = \sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}$$

3.2.3. Computation of the geodesic distance between Q_2 and Q_3 .

Proposition 6. The distance between Q_2 and Q_3 is given by the length of the arc $\widehat{Q_2Q_3}$ which is:

$$\|\widehat{Q_2Q_3}\| = \theta_3 - \theta_2 = \cos^{-1} \left(\left(\frac{M_6}{M_7} \right) (\lambda) + \left(\frac{M_9}{M_8} \right) (\phi) \right), \quad (17)$$

where $\theta_3 - \theta_2$ can be calculated using

$$\cos(\theta_3 - \theta_2) = \cos\theta_3 \cdot \cos\theta_2 + \sin\theta_3 \cdot \sin\theta_2,$$

$$\theta_2 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \sin\theta_2 = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{-c^2 - c|a|\sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}}{a(a^2 + c^2)} \\ \cos\theta_2 = \frac{-c - |a|\sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}}{a^2 + c^2} \end{cases}$$

$$\theta_3 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \sin\theta_3 = \frac{y^2 + (x - c)|y|\sqrt{y^2 + (c - x)^2 - 1}}{y((c - x)^2 + y^2)} \\ \cos\theta_3 = \frac{(x - c) - |y|\sqrt{y^2 + (c - x)^2 - 1}}{(c - x)^2 + y^2} \end{cases}$$

3.2.4. Computation of the distance between Q_3 and E

As the obstacle does not come between points E and Q_3 , it is possible to calculate the euclidean distance between them.

Proposition 7. *The distance between the points Q_3 and E is given by*

$$\|\overrightarrow{EQ_3}\| = \sqrt{\left[\frac{M_6}{M_7} + c - x\right]^2 + \left[\frac{M_9}{M_8} - y\right]^2}$$

3.2.5. *Computation of the distance between E and Q_4*

Proposition 8. *The euclidean distance between the points E e Q_4 is given by:*

3.2.6. *Computation of the geodesic distance between Q_4 and Q_5*

Proposition 9. *The geodesic distance between Q_4 and Q_5 is given by the length of the arc $\widehat{Q_4Q_5}$.*

$$\|\widehat{Q_4Q_5}\| = \theta_5 - \theta_4 = \cos^{-1}\left(\left(\frac{M_{10}}{M_7}\right)(\lambda_1) + \left(\frac{M_{11}}{M_8}\right)(\phi_1)\right),$$

This distance is used when the obstacle is in between the points E and B , that is, from the point E it is not possible to have direct access to point B . In this situation it is also necessary to compute the distance between Q_5 and B .

Proposition 10. *The distance between Q_5 and B is given by:*

$$d(Q_5, B) = \sqrt{b^2 + c^2 - 1}$$

Now, we write about the points E from the frontier. In fact, when we will to show the points of the frontier, we will display a finite number of points denoted by $E_i = (x_i, y_i)$ where x_i is given by:

$$x_i = x_0 + ih \tag{18}$$

for a determined i , and h is the length of the step when moving the x-coordinate from the points E_i on the x axis towards the obstacle. Therefore

the value x_i of the abscissa of E_i will always be known. In order to evaluate the values for the y-coordinate from E_i we look the points over the line $x = x_i$ which can be defined by $P_i = (x_i, y)$, our goal will be the value for y that belong to the frontier, which means the values y_i . Once the value of x_i is known and the distances $d(Q_3, P_i)$ e $d(P_i, Q_4)$ are non linear, a numeric method can be used in order to compute the value of y_i . Thus, $d(Q_3, P_i)$ and $d(P_i, Q_4)$ can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(Q_3, P_i) &= \|\overrightarrow{P_i Q_3}\| = \sqrt{\left[\frac{M_6}{M_7} + c - x_i\right]^2 + \left[\frac{M_9}{M_8} - y\right]^2} = \\
 &= \sqrt{\left[\frac{M_6}{M_7} + c - (x_0 + i * h)\right]^2 + \left[\frac{M_9}{M_8} - y\right]^2} \\
 d(P_i, Q_4) &= \sqrt{\left[x_i - c - \frac{M_{10}}{M_7}\right]^2 + \left[y - \frac{M_{11}}{M_8}\right]^2} = \\
 &= \sqrt{\left[(x_0 + i * h) - c - \frac{M_{10}}{M_7}\right]^2 + \left[y - \frac{M_{11}}{M_8}\right]^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.3. Derivatives Computations

In this subsection the derivatives of the distances are represented and also some function that will shorten the derivatives in order to simplify the expressions that will be used in the algorithm of Section 3.4. As the points of the frontier of the Voronoi diagram are equidistant, in order to find the coordinates of the points of its frontier, the point $P_i = (x_i, y)$ has to “move” towards the generator points A or B . Taking a look at Figure 1, the point D is the last point from which it is possible to have direct access to points A and B , meaning that the obstacle does not get in the way between D and A or D and B . On the other hand, if the point $P_i = (x_i, y)$ is at a coordinate on the right of point D considering the x axis, there are two cases to consider: P_i has direct access to point B or not. These situations are described and analyzed below.

First situation: the point P_i doesn't have direct access to point A

In this situation, the geodesic from P_i to A is the sum of the distance from P_i to Q_3 which belongs to the obstacle (circle) plus a distance from Q_3

towards the point Q_2 , which corresponds to the size of the arc between these points and finally plus the distance from Q_2 to A . On the other hand, P_i has direct access to B . The values of $A = (0,2), B = (0,-5)$ and $C = (0.5,0)$ can be used as an example of this situation. As the Voronoi frontier points are at the same distance from generation points A and B , $D(P_i)$ can be represented as:

$$D(P_i) = d(A, Q_2) + d(Q_2, Q_3) + d(Q_3, P_i) - d(P_i, B). \quad (19)$$

The **Figure 2** shows this situation

Figure 2: Geodesic distances: $d(A, P_i) = d(P_i, B)$

Second situation: the point P_i doesn't have direct access neither to the point A nor to the point B .

The values of $A = (0,1), B = (0,-1.3)$ and $C = (0.5,0)$ can be used as an example of this situation. The calculation of the geodesic from P_i to B is analogous to that of the first situation. This geodesic is the sum of the distance from

P_i to Q_4 plus the size of the arc from Q_4 to Q_5 plus the sum of the distance from Q_5 to B . So,

$$D(P_i)(y) = d(A, Q_2)(y) + d(Q_2, Q_3)(y) + d(Q_3, P_i)(y) - d(P_i, Q_4)(y) + d(Q_4, Q_5)(y) + d(Q_5, B)(y).$$

Figure 3: Second Situation

As the Newton-Raphson method is used to find the coordinate of the y axis for each x_i in $P_i = (x_i, y)$, the derivatives of the distances related to situations 1 and 2 are needed.

Derivative related to the first situation

$$D'(P_i)(y) = d'(A, Q_2)(y) + d'(Q_2, Q_3)(y) + d'(Q_3, P_i)(y) - d'(P_i, B)(y) \quad (21)$$

Derivative related to the second situation:

$$D'(P_i) = d'(A, Q_2)(y) + d'(Q_2, Q_3)(y) + d'(Q_3, P_i)(y) - \\ - \epsilon d'(P_i, Q_4)(y) + d'(Q_4, Q_5)(y) + d'(Q_5, B)(y) \quad (22)$$

Equations 19 and 21 are used when it's the case of the first situation and equations 20 and 22 are used in the second situation. So, for each fixed value i and taking j as the index of the Newton Raphson iterations, with $z_0 = y_{i-1}$, the iterations are:

$$z_{j+1} = z_j - \frac{D(P_i(z_j))}{D'(P_i(z_j))}, \text{ for a fixed value of } i. \quad (23)$$

After finishing the iterations for a fixed value of i , the last value of z_j is the value of y_i . Thus, the value of the coordinates of the point of the Voronoi frontier $E(x_i, y_i)$ related to a specific value of i are known.

3.4. Algorithm

At the beginning of this Subsection the main parts of the algorithm are explained. After that, the algorithm to find points belonging to the frontier of the Voronoi diagram addressed in this work is presented.

3.4.1. Initialization

The initialization part of the algorithm is at lines 1 to 13. The values of a, b and c are setted up.

In the algorithm, two point-set problems need to be answered.

Considering the line that pass by the points B and Q_5 , the first point-set problem consists on knowing if a determined point is below this line (which in the algorithm is represented by the test of line). The second pointset problem consists on to verify if a point is inside the circular obstacle (in the algorithm it is represented by the test of circle). Still in the initialization part, the equations for calculating the λ, ϕ, x_0 and h values are provided.

3.4.2. First situation

The first situation is at instructions from line 19 to line 27 of the algorithm. Given the value of x_i at the end of these instructions, the value of the y_i coordinate is obtained.

3.4.3. Second situation

The second situation is presented at instructions from line 28 to line 36 of the algorithm. Given the value of x_i at the end of these instructions, the value of the y_i coordinate is obtained.

3.4.4. Tests

At lines from 40 to 43, two tests of set point problems are carried out over the boundary point that has just been generated. The first one, called test of line over (x,y) , concerns on determine if the point (x,y) is above or below the line that connects the points B and Q_5 (see Figure 3) . The second one, assign as test of the circle over (x,y) , concerns on determine if the point (x,y) is inside or outside from the circle (obstacle).

3.4.5. Stopping criterion

In the algorithm there is a stopping criterion when applying the Newton-Raphson method which consists of maximum number of iterations named max_iter or if the function is close to zero . This parameter is not greater than 5. This occurs because the algorithm converges rapidly.

Algorithm 1: Voronoi Diagram frontier with circular obstacle

```
1 Assign values to  $a, b$  e  $c$  respecting  $a > 0, -b > a$  and  $0 < c < 1$ .
2  $flag\ test\ of\ the\ circle \leftarrow false$ 
3  $flag\ test\ of\ the\ line \leftarrow true$ 
4  $size \leftarrow 0$ 
5  $lambda \leftarrow (-c - abs(a) * sqrt(a * a + c * c - 1)) / (a * a + c * c)$ 
6  $phi \leftarrow (-c * c - c * abs(a) * sqrt(a * a + c * c - 1)) / (a * (a * a + c * c)) + 1/a$ 
7  $x0 \leftarrow ((c + lambda) * (b - a) / 2) / (phi - a)$ 
8  $h \leftarrow -x0 / 200$ 
9  $points \leftarrow round((-x0 + c) / h) - 1$ 
10  $y \leftarrow (a + b) / 2$ 
11 for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $points$  do
12    $w[i] \leftarrow 0$ 
13    $z[i] \leftarrow 0$ 
14  $i \leftarrow 1$ 
15 while  $i < points + 1$  and  $test\ of\ circle == false$  do
16    $w[i] \leftarrow x0 + ih$ 
17    $x \leftarrow w[i]$ 
18    $j \leftarrow 0$ 
19   if  $flag\ test\ of\ the\ line == true$  then
20     while ( $j < max\_iter$  or  $F(y) \leq \epsilon$ ) do
21        $d1 \leftarrow d((x, y), A)$ 
22        $d2 \leftarrow d((x, y), B)$ 
23        $d1\ prime \leftarrow$  derivative of  $d1$ 
24        $d2\ prime \leftarrow$  derivative of  $d2$ 
25        $F \leftarrow d1 - d2$ 
26        $F\ prime \leftarrow d1\ prime - d2\ prime$ 
27        $y \leftarrow y - F / F\ prime$ 
28        $j \leftarrow j + 1$ 
29   else
30     while ( $j < max\_iter$  or  $F(y) \leq \epsilon$ ) do
31        $d1 \leftarrow d((x, y), A)$ 
32        $d2\ mod \leftarrow d((x, y), B)$ 
33        $d1\ prime \leftarrow$  derivative of  $d1$ 
34        $d2\ mod\ prime \leftarrow$  derivative of  $d2\ mod$ 
35        $F \leftarrow d1 - d2\ mod$ 
36        $F\ prime \leftarrow d1\ prime - d2\ mod\ prime$ 
37        $y \leftarrow y - F / F\ prime$ 
38        $j \leftarrow j + 1$ 
39    $z[i] \leftarrow y$ 
40   if  $test\ of\ line\ over\ (w[i], z[i]) == false$  then
41      $flag\ test\ of\ the\ line \leftarrow false$ 
42   if  $test\ of\ circle\ over\ (w[i], z[i]) == true$  then
43      $flag\ test\ of\ the\ circle \leftarrow true$ 
44    $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
45    $size \leftarrow i$ 
```

4. Results and Discussions

In this paper the problem of finding the frontier of the Voronoi diagram with two generating points and a circular obstacle has been studied in light of an object that is moving towards the obstacle but keeping the same distance from the generating points.

In order to find a finite number of points which describe the frontier, the coordinates of some specific points (main points) were defined and evaluated. After that, the values of the distances (sometimes the geodesic

distances) were recalculated. These distances are functions of one variable y . The Newton-Raphson method was used in the algorithm, which implied the need of the derivatives from these distances.

The proposed algorithm, which generates several points of the Voronoi diagram frontier, uses all information from the previous Sections of this work. From the points generated by the algorithm it can be observed that the frontier has a curved aspect with an upward trajectory in relation to the axis of the ordinates. The Figure 4 has three subfigures, the left and middle ones relating to the first situation. The difference between these subfigures is that for different coordinates of A and B the frontier may or may not touch the obstacle. The right subfigure is related to the second situation. The first and the second situations are described at 3.3. The blue part in the figures refers to the points at the middle line between the points A and B (at this blue part the frontier is still a line).

Figure 4

The results of this work can be used in self-driving car trajectories, self-driving robots and autonomous underwater vehicles trajectories which are some examples.

5. Conclusion

In this work it became clear how the frontier of the Voronoi diagram for only two points and a circular obstacle can be generated, solving the path planning towards the obstacle. The next step is either increase the number of points with only one circular obstacle or increase the number of circular obstacles and only two generator points. The problem with many obstacles and many points seems to be really a big challenge.

Appendix A. Demonstrations of Propositions from Section 3.2

Proposition 5 The distance between the points A and Q_2 is:

$$d(A, Q_2) = \sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}$$

Demonstration:

Figure A.5: Distance between A and Q_2

Created by the author

In order to determine the euclidean distance between A and Q_2 , the Pythagorean theorem is used.

$$A = (0, a), C = (c, 0) \text{ and } r = 1. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The distance $d(A, C)$ must be available in order to permit calculation of the distance $d(A, Q_2)$.

Therefore:

$$d(A, C) = \sqrt{(x_c - x_A)^2 + (y_c - y_A)^2}$$

$$d(A, C) = \sqrt{(c - 0)^2 + (0 - a)^2}$$

$$d(A, C) = \sqrt{a^2 + c^2}$$

Once the distance $d(A, C)$ has been obtained, the Pythagorean theorem can be used again in order to determine the distance $d(A, Q_2)$.

$$d^2(A, C) = d^2(A, Q_2) + r^2$$

$$d^2(A, Q_2) = d^2(A, C) - r^2$$

$$d^2(A, Q_2) = a^2 + c^2 - 1$$

$$d(A, Q_2) = \sqrt{a^2 + c^2 - 1}$$

Proposition 6 The distance between Q_2 and Q_3 is given by the length of the arc $\widehat{Q_4Q_5}$.

Demonstration: The functions $\sin(\cdot)$ and $\cos(\cdot)$ of θ_2 and θ_3 respectively, can be represented using the functions φ, λ and M_i , com $i = 6, \dots, 9$:

$$\theta_2 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \sin \theta_2 = \phi \\ \cos \theta_2 = \lambda \end{cases}$$

$$\theta_3 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \sin \theta_3 = \frac{M_9}{M_8} \\ \cos \theta_3 = \frac{M_6}{M_7} \end{cases}$$

Making the appropriate substitutions, equation 17 is found.

Proposition 7 The distance between the points Q_3 and E is given by:

$$\|\overrightarrow{EQ_3}\| = \sqrt{\left[\frac{M_6}{M_7} + c - x\right]^2 + \left[\frac{M_9}{M_8} - y\right]^2}$$

Demonstration:

The coordinates of points Q_3 and E are, respectively:

$$Q_3 = \left(c + \frac{(x-c) - |y|\sqrt{y^2 + (c-x)^2 - 1}}{(c-x)^2 + y^2}, \frac{y^2 + (x-c)|y|\sqrt{y^2 + (c-x)^2 - 1}}{y((c-x)^2 + y^2)} \right)$$

$$E = (x, y)$$

Using functions M_i , with $i = 6, \dots, 9$, the coordinates of M_3 can be rewritten as:

$$Q_3 = \left(c + \frac{M_6}{M_7}, \frac{M_9}{M_8} \right)$$

The norm of the vector $\overrightarrow{EQ_3}$ is the euclidean distance between the points Q_3 and E . Thus:

$$\|\overrightarrow{EQ_3}\| = \sqrt{\left[\left(c + \frac{M_6}{M_7} \right) - x \right]^2 + \left[\left(\frac{M_9}{M_8} \right) - y \right]^2}$$

$$\|\overrightarrow{EQ_3}\| = \sqrt{\left[\frac{M_6}{M_7} + c - x \right]^2 + \left[\frac{M_9}{M_8} - y \right]^2}$$

Proposition 8

The euclidean distance between the points E e Q_4 is given by:

$$d(E, Q_4) = \sqrt{\left[x - c - \frac{M_{10}}{M_7} \right]^2 + \left[y - \frac{M_{11}}{M_8} \right]^2}$$

Demonstration:

Given the coordinates of the points:

$$E = (x, y)$$

e

$$Q_4 = \left(c + \frac{(x-c) + |y|\sqrt{y^2 + (c-x)^2 - 1}}{(c-x)^2 + y^2}, \frac{y^2 + (x-c)|y|\sqrt{y^2 + (c-x)^2 - 1}}{y((c-x)^2 + y^2)} \right)$$

Rewriting the coordinates of Q_4 using the functions M_i , com $i = 7, 8, 10, 11, \dots, 11$. it becomes:

$$Q_4 = \left(c + \frac{M_{10}}{M_7}, \frac{M_{11}}{M_8} \right)$$

Right now, we have just demonstrated the distance between the points E and Q_4

$$d(E, Q_4) = \sqrt{\left[x - \left(c + \frac{M_{10}}{M_7}\right)\right]^2 + \left[y - \frac{M_{11}}{M_8}\right]^2}$$

Thus, we obtain:

$$d(E, Q_4) = \sqrt{\left[x - c - \frac{M_{10}}{M_7}\right]^2 + \left[y - \frac{M_{11}}{M_8}\right]^2}$$

Proposition 9 The geodesic distance between Q_4 and Q_5 is given by the length of the arc $\widehat{Q_4Q_5}$.

$$\|\widehat{Q_4Q_5}\| = \theta_5 - \theta_4 = \cos^{-1}\left(\left(\frac{M_{10}}{M_7}\right)(\lambda_1) + \left(\frac{M_{11}}{M_8}\right)(\phi_1)\right),$$

Demonstration:

$$\lambda_1 = \cos(\theta_5) = \frac{-c - |b|\sqrt{b^2 + c^2 - 1}}{b^2 + c^2}$$

$$\phi_1 = \sin(\theta_5) = \frac{-c^2 - c|b|\sqrt{b^2 + c^2 - 1}}{b(b^2 + c^2)} + \frac{1}{b}$$

$$\cos(\theta_4) = \frac{M_{10}}{M_7}$$

$$\sin(\theta_4) = \frac{M_{11}}{M_8}$$

Proposition 10 The distance between Q_5 and B is given by:

$$d(Q_5, B) = \sqrt{b^2 + c^2 - 1}$$

Demonstration:

This proof is analogous to the proof of the distance between points A and Q2.

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